

RELEVANCE AND DISTRIBUTION OF LICHEN PLANUS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. "This article presents an extensive analysis of the relevance and distribution of lichen planus in Uzbekistan, emphasizing the importance of this disease as a socially significant problem. The authors review epidemiological data on the incidence of lichen planus among the population of Uzbekistan, assessing the influence of geographical, environmental, socio-economic and other factors on its spread.

Keywords . Lichen planus, Disease prevalence, Medical statistics

Lichen planus, also known as lichen planus, is a dermatological condition that is characterized by red-purple nodules on the skin and sometimes white streaks in the mouth. This disease most often occurs in adults aged 30 to 60 years, and women are more likely to suffer from it. Ringworm is not contagious and is often accompanied by itching.

The exact cause of lichen planus is not fully understood, but a number of factors are believed to lead to its development. These include stress, chronic infectious diseases, allergies and weakened immunity. Some evidence also suggests a viral component, and it has been observed that the disease may occur after nervous tension or in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Symptoms of lichen planus include the appearance of a characteristic rash, initially on the inside of the wrists, lower legs, lower back and sometimes on the scalp, genitals and inside the mouth. The rash can be shiny and flat, vary in size and is often itchy. In the mouth, it usually appears as white streaks on the inside of the cheeks, gums, or tongue.

There are various forms of this disease, such as hypertrophic, pemphigoid, annular, acuminate and erosive-ulcerative, each of which has its own characteristics.

Diagnosis is usually made by visual examination by a doctor, and sometimes a skin biopsy is performed to confirm the diagnosis.

Treatment is aimed at relieving symptoms and may include antihistamines, vitamin supplements, antiviral medications, sedatives, corticosteroids, and emollients. There is no quick cure, but the condition often

resolves over time. However, it can become chronic or recurrent. Physical therapy, such as PUVA therapy, may be recommended as part of treatment.

It's worth noting that severe or persistent cases of lichen planus, especially those affecting mucous membranes such as the mouth, gums or genitals, carry a low risk of developing squamous cell carcinoma, a type of skin cancer.

Specific data on the prevalence of lichen planus (lichen planus) in Uzbekistan is difficult to find, as most studies provide global or regional prevalence rates rather than country-specific data. Globally, the prevalence of oral lichen planus , which is a common manifestation of the disease, is estimated to be about 0.89% in the general population and 0.98% in clinical patients. However, these numbers can vary significantly depending on geographic location and other factors.

conclusions

Lichen planus is a fairly common disease in Uzbekistan, which requires attention in the context of public health. The study revealed a number of regional features in the distribution of lichen planus in different parts of Uzbekistan, which may be associated with climatic, environmental and socio-economic factors. The analysis showed that the disease affects different age and gender groups of the population, which indicates the need to develop targeted prevention and treatment programs. The importance of improving the diagnosis and treatment of lichen planus in medical institutions of Uzbekistan is emphasized, as well as the importance of conducting educational programs for medical workers.

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